

http://plugin13.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

Organization

All (1)

Organization	PRÉ-ERROS	0	0
AVISOS			
ID: http://plugin13.marketingdigitaltools.com/#Organization			
@type	Organization		
@id	http://plugin13.marketingdigitaltools.com/#Organization		
url	http://plugin13.marketingdigitaltools.com/		
name	Marketing Digital Tools		
telephone	+351913824934		
description	Agência de Marketing Digital Ecommerce		
sameAs	https://www.facebook.com/marketingdigitaltools/		
sameAs	https://twitter.com/mktdigitaltools		
sameAs	https://www.instagram.com/marketingdigitaltools		
sameAs	https://www.linkedin.com/company/34891093/admin/		
sameAs	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpRZ4JVRJFdvCmQ06i5zFiw/featured		
logo			
@type	ImageObject		
url	http://plugin13.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-Marketing-Digital-Tools-com-Slogan.png		
contactPoint			
@type	ContactPoint		
telephone	+351913824934		
potentialAction			
@type	SearchAction		
target			
@type	EntryPoint		
urlTemplate	http://plugin13.marketingdigitaltools.com/?s={search_term_string}		
query-input			
@type	PropertyValueSpecification		
valueRequired	http://schema.org/True		
valueName	search_term_string		